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STRESS MANAGEMENT – A WAY TO SUCCESS

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Abstract:

The alarming rise in the competition has impacted the businesses to strategies the reported stress amongst its employees. The climbing figures are hard to ignore and so is the corresponding stress levels. Though the concept of stress management has been evolving for decades, no single all – encompassing meaning has as yet been achieved. This paper seeks to explore the meaning of stress management and its positive impact towards success. The paper argues about the implication and the efforts of stress on the human psychology. The first part of the paper states the meaning of stress and how it can be managed. The second part of the paper states the recent transformation in the management system related to stress,

highlighting the positive effect on humans and work culture. The third part of the paper discusses the prospects and challenges outlining the path of success.

The methodology used for the research is secondary in nature and the main core objective is to know how stress can be managed in a positive way so that it can lead to higher performance and success. This paper can provide an insight about the ill effects of stress due to this competitive era, especially in India where the awareness about its management is still in doubt.

Keywords: *Stress, Management, Stressors, Human effect.*

Introduction:

Adopting the right attitude can convert a negative stress into a positive one – Hans Selye

In today's dynamic corporate culture stress management is the emerging area of interest for management, employees and even individuals. "Stress refers to a state of psychological or physiological imbalance resulting from the disparities between the situational demand and the individual's ability or motivation to meet those demands". (Dr. Hans Selye) On the other hand the management of stress includes a wide spectrum of tools and techniques which are specifically aimed towards the controlling of a person's level of chronic stress in order to improve the day to day functioning.

Stress can have both positive as well as negative effect on a human brain and body. It has been observed lately that sometimes the accurate amount of stress can act as a motivator. However, high levels of stress have the capacity to hamper the productivity of an individual. Besides, it has a huge impact on their emotional and physical health (Hicks & Caroline, 2007). It has been rightly said that excess of anything is bad, so is the case with stress, as it is costly. Costly as it owes to the fact that high stress levels lead to absenteeism, high turnover, low productivity, it also makes an employee

resents towards its employer leading to distraction from employee engagement. (Cooper & Payne, 2008)

Therefore it becomes quite essential for the employer as well as the employees to recognise any signs of stress amongst themselves so as to prevent the organization and its performance level to get impacted. (Hicks & Caroline, 2007) This paper further identifies the types and symptoms of stress, highlighting the approaches to be followed in coping with it.

Literature Review:

There have been a range of perspectives on stress management in various journals and books. Studies by Hicks & Caroline, 2007 and Fried, 2008 suggested that society value, new business opportunities, firm's reputation, better stakeholder's relationship, competition acts like a driving force for a business firm to manage the stress levels of its employees. The studies conducted by Michie & Williams (2002) showed that the reason for ill health and sickness of the staff was due to the high stress levels and their incapacity to cope up with it.

Objectives of the study:

- ❖ To understand the theoretical and practical perspective of stress and its management.
- ❖ To understand the essentials developing positive stress as motivator.
- ❖ To determine the reasons and symptoms of stress.
- ❖ To highlight the changing developments in stress management.
- ❖ To determine the prospects and exposed challenges faced by companies in managing stress.

Methodology:

A comprehensive review of the professional and academic literature on stress management was carried out. An analytical approach was followed to review the symptoms and identify the current stressors having both positive as well as negative effect on employees. Reliable secondary sources were used to understand the concept of stress management as a whole.

The sources of stress are numerous as the pressures at work have increased, be it time related stress, anticipatory stress, and situational stress or encounter stress. The recognition of the symptoms is the major challenge and to direct it towards positive direction is the actual management of stress. It is really imperative that stress in individual should be identified as early as possible in order to devise the best possible remedy (Weiss, 2012). Symptoms such as external signs, like loss of interest, irritation, moody and short tempered behaviour, staying unhappy and depressed are certain external signals which should be identified by self and the management. In order to actually be positive about stress self-assessment is essential. It refers to determining by self the signs of stress such as panic attacks, headaches, withdrawal from friends, feeling depressed. Such indicators require immediate attention.

It is of paramount importance that an individual suffering from intense stress should be approached and informed about how the negative stress is harmful to their mind and body and also impacting the work and its environment. Separate meetings should be conducted by the management in order to know the employees mind-set and situation. Proper work division should be done keeping into consideration the capacity and capabilities of the individual. Training sessions should be given to the employees in order to teach them how to cope up with the negative effects of stress and convert it into positive actions. Aldana (1996) establishes a direct relationship between personal habits and perceived stress. In short, it states that healthy habits including regular exercise, healthy nutrition, and regular sleep directly impact an individual's perception and resistance to stress.

The figure above shows the ways of prevention of stress in an organization. Due to the high demands, defined roles and complexities increases giving high effectiveness to productivity and well as impacting the individuals health and psychic. The ways of preventing it can be counselling, relaxation training, teaching them time management skill. Excess of stress can impact the organization and increase its cost in a huge way.

Conclusion and Potential further research:

It can be concluded by the saying excess of everything is harmful and so is stress. It is a naturally occurring phenomenon which can act as a motivator if used correctly and under right

circumstances. As a professional and leader, it becomes a paramount duty to identify the stress and try to stem down its root cause in order to resolve the problem. And, in cases where either the solution resides outside of our sphere of influence or, to help cope with residual stress, it is essential that we understand the various coping mechanisms available and help individuals select the most appropriate ones.

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